

Environmental Trade-offs of Different Reclaimed Asphalt Pavement Recycling Strategies for the City of São Paulo, Brazil

Zila M. G. Mascarenhas¹[0000-0001-8562-3685], Fernanda Belizario-Silva²[0000-0002-6866-6445],
and Kamilla L. Vasconcelos¹[0000-0003-4305-4829]

¹ zilamascarenhas@usp.br, University of São Paulo, Brazil

² Institute for Technological Research, Brazil

Supporting Information

Fig. 1. Materials mass flows in metric ton for the (a) RAP downcycling in SA (S1), (b) RAP downcycling in CAM (S2), and (c) RAP recycling in HMA (S3).

Table 1. Amount of each raw material.

Sc.	Mix	RAP, t	Agg., t	Soil, t	Lime, t	Water, t	Binder (virgin), t
S1	HMA	0	140,319	-	-	-	6,920
	CAM	0	41,865	-	406	1,913	929
	SA	30,000	0	12,857	-	3,176	-
S2	HMA	0	140,319	-	-	-	6,920
	CAM	30,000	11,865	-	406	1,913	929
	SA	0	30,000	12,857	-	3,176	-
S3	HMA	30,000	112,638	-	-	-	4,601
	CAM	0	41,865	-	406	1,913	929
	SA	0	30,000	12,857	-	3,176	-

* SA: soil aggregate, CAM: cold asphalt mixture, HMA: hot mix asphalt, Sc.: scenarios, Agg.: aggregate.

Table 2. Theoretical energy demand calculated considering materials' temperatures and heating capacity (see Table 3).

Process	Energy source	Source calorific value, MJ/kg	Theoretical heat energy per t, MJ/t	
			HMA0%	HMA20%
Bitumen storage	Gas (LPG)	46.5	19	18
Virgin aggregate drying and heat	Gas (LPG)	46.5	279	298
RAP drying and heat	-	-	0	0
Asphalt mixture mixing	Electricity*	-	-	-
Total energy required from plant, MJ/t	-	-	298	316

* 1 kWh is equivalent to 3.6 MJ, measured electricity consumption: 1.2 kWh/t

Table 3. Temperatures during mixing phase, mass and heat capacity of each asphalt mixture material.

Process	HMA 0 RAP		HMA 20 RAP		Energy source	Heat capacity (kJ/C/kg)	Unit	HMA 0 RAP		HMA 20 RAP	
	Initial T, °C	Final T, °C	Initial T, °C	Final T, °C				mass unit (kg)	functional unit (kg)	mass unit (kg)	functional unit (kg)
Bitumen storage	20	160	20	160	Gas (LPG)	2.093	KJ/Kg/C	69274		64883	
Virgin aggregate (drying and heating)	20	180	20	220*	Gas (LPG)	0.79	KJ/Kg/C	1270020		1134437	
RAP (drying and heating)	20	20	20	20	-	-	-	0		128172	
Asphalt mixture	-	164	-	164	Electricity	-	-	1358310		1346340	
Water 4%	20	100	20	100		4.1855	KJ/Kg/C	50801		50504	
Water vapor	100	180	100	220		1.83	KJ/Kg	50801		50504	
Latent heat of water evaporation						2256	KJ/Kg				
Casing loses factor						0.27					

* Final temperature estimated according to the Asphalt Institute (2015). T: temperature.

Table 4. Life cycle inventory.

Stage	Unit process	Quantities per scenario			Data source (inventory for the upstream processes)
		S1	S2	S3	
Raw materials production	Agg.	182,184 (t)	182,184 (t)	184,503 (t)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Gravel production, crushed gravel, crushed Cutoff, U - BR
	Asphalt binder	7,849 (t)	7,849 (t)	5,530 (t)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Pitch production, petroleum refinery operation pitch Cutoff, U - BR
	Water	5,089 (t)	5,089 (t)	5,089 (t)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Market for tap water tap water Cutoff, U - BR
	Lime	406 (t)	406 (t)	406 (t)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Lime, hydrated, packed market for Cut-off, U - RoW
	Soil*	12,857 (t)	12,857 (t)	12,857 (t)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Clay pit operation clay Cutoff, U - RoW
RAP processing	RAP	-	-	936 (h)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Machine operation, diesel, >= 74.57 kW, high load factor Cutoff, U - GLO
Materials transportation	Agg., soil	357,914 (tkm)	357,914 (tkm)	361,161 (tkm)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO3 transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO3 Cutoff, U - BR
	Asphalt binder	392,460 (tkm)	392,460 (tkm)	276,304 (tkm)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO3 transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO3 Cutoff, U - BR
Mixing	Materials ' heating	43,877,301 (MJ)	43,877,301 (MJ)	46,527,607 (MJ)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Heat, central or small-scale, natural gas {RoW} market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas Cut-off, U
	Asphalt binder storage				
	Mixing plant operation	259,982 (kWh)	259,982 (kWh)	285,679 (kWh)	Ecoinvent 3.9.1: Electricity, medium voltage market for Cut-off, U - BR-South-eastern/Mid-western grid}

* Soil acquisition was assumed similar to clay pit operation inventory. Agg: aggregate.

References

1. Asphalt Institute (2015). Mix design methods for asphalt concrete and other hot-mix types. MS-2. Lexington, KY, USA.